

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№6

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Elektron nashr. 631 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-iyunda ruxsat etildi.

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golischeva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayeich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotni shakllantirishda xitoy va rossiya investitsiyalarining qiyosiy tahlili.....	20
Malikov Numonjon Kamalovich	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikka ta'siri.....	26
Sherzod Rajabov, Istora Abdusalomova	
Reducing inequality through human capital development: a comparative analysis of policies in the european union and uzbekistan.....	30
Iloxomjonov Jaxongir Alisher o'g'li	
Hududiy raqamli infratuzilmaning xizmat ko'rsatish sektoriga ta'siri: samarqand viloyati misolida.....	39
Musinov Dilshod Sultanovich	
Ways to improve quality in hotels through digital technologies.....	44
N.A. Rakhmonova	
Проблемы и пути внедрения механизма налогового стимулирования центров инновационного роста нового узбекистана.....	48
Умаров Б. С.	
Влияние протекционистской политики на инвестиционные стратегии промышленных предприятий.....	55
Ёдгоров Сардорбек Самадович	
Fiskal siyosat tahlili: aholi bandligi; aholi daromadlari; soliqqa tortish.....	61
Isroilov Boxodir Ibragimovich, Navruzova Farog'at Abdihamid qizi	
Problems in entrepreneurial potential development: a comprehensive analysis of contemporary barriers and challenges.....	67
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida aholi omonatlarining jozibadorligini oshirishning metodologik asoslari va amaliy yo'nalishlari.....	73
Xakimov Zoxid Norbo'tayevich	
To'lov aylanmasining mohiyatini aniqlashda to'lov va to'lov oqimlarining roli.....	78
I.F.Sayfiddinov	
Moliyaviy inklyuzivlikni ta'minlovchi samarali soliq siyosati.....	83
Artikov Ne'matulla Abdusalamovich	
Youth, digital finance, and the gig economy in uzbekistan.....	86
Akmal Boymurodov	
Aktiyadorlik jamiyatlari korporativ boshqaruvda qaror qabul qilishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish masalalari.....	91
Xabibullaeva Shirinxon Tohir qizi	
В условиях трансформации обеспечение развитие образования и нуки в сфере подготовки управленческих кадров.....	98
Суюнов Дилмурод Холмурадович	
Ипотечное кредитование как инструмент социальной политики в узбекистане.....	104
Базарова Нигора Равшановна	
Kichik biznes subyektlari tomonidan hudud aholisi bandligini ta'minlashning ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy natijalari.....	110
Ergasheva Nigora Abdigapparovna	
Kichik korxonalar istiqbolli hududlarda sanoat ishlab chiqarish holati dinamikasi.....	114
Xonto'rayev Obbosxon Kamolxon o'g'li	
Banklarning aktivlarini daromadligini oshirish yo'llari.....	118
Elbusinova Umida Khamidullaevna	

Ekologik omillar o'zgarishining dehqon xo'jaliklari yalpi hosiliga ta'siri	123
Otamurodova Dildora Abdukrimovna	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklarining yashil iqtisodiyotdagi o'rni	128
Eshev Furqat A'zamovich, Ibragimova Feruza Axtamovna, Jumanazarova Malika Baxtiyorovna, Raxmatova Mohina Dilmurod qizi	
Использование интеллектуальных технологий в процессе обслуживания клиентов банка	132
Хашимова Дилёра Пахритдиновна	
Innovatsion faoliyatning moliyaviy rag'batlantirish va boshqaruv samaradorligini belgilovchi omil va jihatlar.....	138
Baxriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
Import tovarlari bo'yicha aksiz solig'ini undirishning nazariy asoslari.....	143
Abdurasulov Murodjon Bahrom o'g'li	
Роль цифровых валют центральных банков в модернизации платёжной инфраструктуры: мировой опыт и перспективы Узбекистана	150
Срожиддинова З.Х., Тухтасинова Д.Н.	
Tijorat banklarida chakana to'lov tizimlarini nazariy asosi.....	155
Sultonov Davronjon Rustam o'g'li	
Tikuv-trikotaj korxonalarida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishda strategik menejmentning roli	161
Mamatraimov Islom Mamanazarovich	
Ta'lim, ekologiya va raqamlashtirish sohalarida bolalar va o'smirlar turizmini integratsiyalash: xalqaro tajribalar va O'zbekiston.....	170
Islomova Dilrabo Salomovna	
Iqtisodiy masalalarni matrilsalar nazariyasi asosida modellashtirish va python dasturlash tilida yechish.....	175
Tojiyev Ilhom Ibraimovich, To'rayeva Feruza Dilmurodovna, Namozova Barchinoy G'ayrat qizi, Baxronova Zuhra Otaniyoz qizi	
Pul bozori barqarorligini ta'minlashda tijorat banklarida likvidlikni boshqarish samaradorligi	188
Sattorova Nasiba G'anjon qizi	
The role of digitalization of healthcare in the implementation of the safe city project	192
Akbarjon Iminov	
Аутоиммунные поражения центральной нервной системы, возникающие после стрептококковой инфекции	198
Умарова Саодат Сулаймоновна, Нормакматов Бахтиёр Ботиралиевич	
Iqtisodiyotiga yo'naltirilgan investiyalar tahlili.....	204
Namozov Olim Botirovich	
Creating a favorable climate for investment in agriculture	209
U.I.Djumaniyazov, B.J.Mirzaev	
Davlat ishtirokidagi korxonalarini korporativ boshqaruvni xalqaro standartlari asosida takomillashtirish	214
F.Djalilov	
Davlat tibbiyot tashkilotlarida ish beruvchining fuqarolik javobgarligini majburiy su'gurta qilish xarajatlarini hisobi.....	222
Kuliboyev Azamat Shonazarovich	
O'zbekistonda bank operatsion xarajatlari buxgalteriya hisobi	227
Qurbonova Sitora Vahobjon qizi	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik subyektlarini rivojlantirishning strategik yo'nalishlari.....	233
Musayev Ozodjon Shavkat o'g'li	
Пути обеспечения стабильного экономического роста в условиях перехода к зелёной экономике, совершенствования государственной экономической политики и повышения эффективности внедрения принципов цикличной экономики.....	237
Худайбергенова Адалат Неъматуллаевна, Убайдуллаев Сирожиддин Жамшидович, Файзиёва Хамида	

Кудратовна, Эшбоев Миржалол Бахромович O'zbekiston sanoatining iqtisodiy holatini baholash	241
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich Maktabgacha ta'limda tayanch kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda matematika va savod asoslarining didaktik yechimlari.....	247
Mingboyeva Guldorxon Maxmudovna Soliq tizimida soliq riskini baholash uslubiyoti.....	252
Nasimov Ravshanjon Azimovich Budjetni rejalashtirish tizimida jismoniy shaxslar daromadlari bo'yicha prognozlashni takomillashtirishning metodologik asoslari	260
Babaev Shavkat Bayramovich Понятие и сущность денежного потока в системе финансового управления.....	267
Машарипова Шахло Адамбаевна Yashil mehmonxonalarda strategik tahlil metodologiyasi	274
Rasulova Nigora Yusupovna Цифровая трансформация: новые возможности и современные тенденции в управлении бизнесом и инвестициями.....	279
Баратова Динора Алишеровна Mehmonxonalarda xizmat ko'rsatishning sifati va samaradorligini baholash.....	283
Ikromov Akbar Farhod o'g'li Модель внедрения open banking в Узбекистане: предложение на основе международного опыта и локальных особенностей.....	288
Камалов Шухрат Камалович, Аскарлова Дилором Хожимуратовна, Баходиров Жасурбек Олёрбек ўғли, Маликов Шохрух Шокирович, Тенгелова Фарангиз Мажид кизи O'zbekistonda islom moliyasini joriy qilishning yo'llari	295
Ashurbayev Farrux Alisher o'g'li, Tuxsanov Eldor Dilmurod o'g'li AQSH tajribasiga ko'ra eksportni iqtisodiy o'sishga tasiri	299
D.E.Qarshiev Iqtisodiyotni tartibga solish orqali aholi farovonligini oshirishning ahamiyati	304
Berdibekov A. Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirish va aholi moliyaviy savodxonligini oshirishda inklyuziv moliyaning ahamiyati.....	308
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna Problems of the financial mechanism influence for stable and inertial development of enterprises.....	313
Zaynalov Jakhongir Rasulovich, Alieva Susanna Tibbiyot turizmni rivojlantirish va uning salohiyatini iqtisodiy baholashning ilmiy va uslubiy asoslari	317
Vofaxojayeva Dilafuz Marufovna Turistik destinatsiyalar va raqamli marketing texnologiyalari orqali turizm barqarorligini transformatsiya qilish.....	322
Nurmuhammadxon Oppoqonov Kichik va o'rta biznes moliyaviy barqarorligining kambag'allikni kamaytirishdagi ahamiyati.....	327
Djamalov Xasan Numanjanovich Qoraqalpog'iston respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy va iqtisodiy salohiyatini baholash.....	335
Xoshimov Baxrom Baxadirovich O'zbekiston turizm sektorida tog' turizmining ulushi.....	343
Alimov Abdvakil Komil o'g'li O'zbekiston respublikasida investitsiya faoliyatini moliyaviy boshqarish va bunda xorij tajribasi.....	348
Ismailov Dilshod Anvarjonovich	

Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini samarali boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning holati.....	354
Sattarov Xayrulla Fayzullayevich	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatida innovatsiyalarni rivojlantirish strategiyasini tanlash va asoslash	358
Shakirova Madinaxon Gafurdjanovna	
O'zbekistonning xalqaro valyuta-moliya tashkilotlari bilan o'zaro hamkorlik aloqalarini mustahkamlash yo'nalishlari.....	362
Gulmurodova Marjona Olimjon qizi, Turg'unova Zohida Shavkat qizi, Umida Yuldasheva	
Jismoniy shaxslarning daromadlarini soliqqa tortish tartibini takomillashtirish.....	367
Bobomurotova Manzura Panji qizi	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlari va qimmatli qog'ozlar bozori o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy munosabatlar	372
Berdaliyev Javohir Jahongir o'g'li	
Farg'ona viloyati mahallalarida tadbirkorlikni va hunarmadchilikni rivojlanishi holati tahlili	379
Tuxtasinov Zafarjon Odiljonovich	
Проблемы охраны окружающей среды и формирования «зеленой экономики»	389
Ёдгорова Мухайё Шухратовна, Иминова Наргиза Акрамовна	
The evolution of passenger transport in uzbekistan and its impact on economic growth.....	392
Naubetova Ziyada Niyet kizi	
Davlat tibbiyot tashkilotlarida ish beruvchining fuqarolik javobgarligini majburiy sug'urta qilish xarajatlarining hisobi.....	397
Kuliboev Azamat Shonazarovich	
Jahon sug'urta amaliyotining O'zbekiston sug'urta bozorining rivojlanishiga ta'siri	402
Kuvatova Dinara Anvarovna	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda xorijiy investitsiyalarning ahamiyati va ta'sir mexanizmlari	406
Abdullayev Zoxid Xolxo'jayevich	
Xaridorlar bilan hisob-kitoblar auditida moliyaviy tahlil usullarini qo'llash xususiyatlari.....	411
Saginbaev Sultanbek Turdibay o'g'li, Sultamuratov Qallibek	
The function and value of commercial banks in fostering capital market growth.....	416
Isakov Janabay Yakipbaevich	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning korxonalar risk boshqaruvidagi rolini swot tahlili orqali tadqiq etishning ahamiyati	427
Tojimatov Izzatbek Ikromali o'g'li	
Germaniyaning deutsche banki va buyuk britaniyaning barclays banki xizmatlar amaliyoti va uni o'zbekiston bank tizimi faoliyatiga qo'llash yo'llari	432
Raxmatov Temur Sotiboldiyevich	
The state and development trends of business process auditing in joint-stock companies in uzbekistan.....	439
Utegenova Sarbinaz Turdimuratovna	
Mamlakatimizda amaldagi budjetlararo munosabatlarning tartibi hisobi, hamda uning ahamiyati	444
Tuxsanov Eldor Dilmurod o'g'li, Saydullayeva Zeboxon Shukrilla qizi	
Qurilish materiallari sanoatida innovatsion klasterlarni boshqarishni takomillashtirish	462
Xaydarova E'zoza Shukurullayevna, Li Zin Bo	
Barqaror rivojlanish va yashil iqtisodiyotning mamlakatimizda so'nggi yillardagi oshib borayotgan ahamiyati	467
Bahodirova Mohigul	
Conceptual framework for boosting the financial and economic performance of investment projects in industrial enterprises.....	472
Sarriev Kahraman Ramatullaevich	
Bandlik va ayollar tadbirkorligi	477
Ibodullayeva M.S.	

Mamlakatimiz yalpi ichki mahsulotini ekonometrik prognozlash.....	482
A'zamov Musurmon Axmadovich, Islomov Javohir	
Ekspost siyosatini tadbirkorlik faoliyati rivojlanishiga ta'siri.....	488
Suvonov Ibrohim Izbosarovich, Abdug'aniyev Murodjon Shavkat o'g'li	
Aholini ish bilan ta'minlashda qishloq aholisini mehnat salohiyatidan foydalanish.....	492
Noiba Qodirova Maxmud qizi	
Yashirin iqtisodiyotni kamaytirishda rasmiy bandlik va moliyaviy munosabatlarni rivojlantirish	497
Xalimbetov Farxad Bagibekovich, Reyimberdiyev Baburbek Adilbek o'g'li	
Analysis of touristic potential and capacity of ecotourism sites	501
Abdurakhmanova Akida Faizulla kizi	
Xorijiy investitsiya ishtirokidagi korxonalarni moliyalashtirishni takomillashtirish.....	509
Salohiddinov Jaloliddin	
Infratuzilma va bozor infratuzilmasi tushunchalarining nazariy tavsifi	516
G'aniyev Botir Baxtiyorovich	
O'zbekiston va xorijiy davlatlarda aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining qimmatli qog'ozlar orqali kapital yig'ish strategiyalari	520
Dilnozaxon Muxitdinova	
Iqtisodiy inqiroz paytida korxonalarda likvidlilikni boshqarish strategiyalari	527
Abdusalomova Nodira Bakhodirovna, Jabborova Sevinch Xusanovna	
O'zbekistonda islomiy mikromoliyaviy xizmatlar orqali ish bilan bandlikni oshirish istiqbollari.....	532
Mamatkulov Humoyun Bobir-ugli	
Textile enterprises and changing market conditions: integration of demand analysis, trend forecasting and strategic assortment management	536
Ikramova Nodira Burkhon kizi	
Aksiyadorlik korxonalarini boshqaruv tizimida korporativ madaniyatni takomillashtirish.....	540
Umarkhodjaeva Muyassarhon Ganievna, Omanova Nargiza Rustam qizi	
Moliyaviy faoliyat natijalari hisobi va auditini takomillashtirish.....	548
Po'latov Xudoyberdi Uktamovich, Abduxoliqov Isomiddin Ikrom o'g'li	
Rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda iqtisodiyotning real sektori korxonalariga kreditlar bo'yicha foiz stavkalariga ta'sir ko'rsatishda markaziy banklarning qayta moliyalash stavkalarining rolini tahlil qilish	553
Jabbarov Eliboy, Abdullayeva Charos Abdullo qizi	
O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jalik mahsulotlarini qayta ishlashda innovatsiyalarning roli va iqtisodiy samaradorligi	558
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich, Solohiddinov Nuriddin Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Sirkulyar iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish orqali chiqindilarni boshqarish muammosini bartaraf etish yo'llari.....	563
Narzullayev Elmurod Shuxrat o'g'li, Hamrokulov Ulug'bek Abdurahmatovich	
Korxonani samarali boshqarishni ta'minlash strategiyalari	567
D.Mutalova	
Masofaviy ta'lim platformalarining qiyosiy tahlili va funksional xususiyatlari.....	571
Nabieva Nilufar Nabi qizi	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning jamiyat hayotiga ta'siri.....	577
Aripova Ziyoda Xayrullayevna, Nurmuxamedova Tursunoy Usmonovna	
Transportda turistik xizmatlarni boshqarish mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	581
Tuychiyev Anvarjon Muxtorjonovich	
Ipak yo'lining tarixiy madaniy merosi va hunarmandchiligi: dolzarb muammolar va tadqiqot istiqbollari	584
Xushnazarova Maxzuna Gulamdjanovna	

Eksport faoliyatini rag'batlantirishda institutsional va moliyaviy mexanizmlarning roli.....	589
Umarkulov Kodirjon Maxamadaminovich	
Elektron pul evolyutsiyasi.....	595
Marpatov Mavlonxon Dadashevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish jarayonida sanoat korxonalarining roli.....	600
Nasullayeva Yoqutoy Nasim qizi	
O'zbekistonda turizm marketingi va raqobatbardoshligini oshirish.....	606
Ikramova Nasiba Axmadovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirishning zamonaviy yo'nalishlari.....	610
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzoqovich, Shodiyev Fazliddin Qalandar o'g'li	
Jamiyatda imkoniyati cheklanganlarning bandligini ta'minlashning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy asoslari.....	615
Tilavova Munisa Maxmudovna	
Moliyaviy matematika vositalarining O'zbekiston kredit tizimidagi qo'llanilishi.....	620
Shamsiyeva Nigora Rafiq qizi	
Ecological sustainability in tourism: regional practices and global reflections.....	626
Sayyora Safaeva	

This article aims to explore the practical applications of ecological sustainability in tourism within Uzbekistan and to contrast them with best practices from Mediterranean Europe. Drawing from personal academic and institutional experience, as well as fieldwork in regions like the Priaralye National Nature Park in Karakalpakstan, this study highlights both achievements and areas for improvement in the sustainable management of tourism resources.

The discussion will also incorporate insights from Professor Oscar Saladié's work in Catalonia, Spain, particularly his analysis of climate-related risks in coastal tourism and the role of universities in advancing sustainability agendas. The comparative lens will allow for the identification of adaptable strategies, useful for both policy-makers and tourism educators working in diverse geographic and socio-economic contexts.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

S. Gössling et al.[1] systematically assess the impact of the tourism sector on environmental sustainability and analyze the role of environmental planning, innovative approaches and policy reforms in the development of sustainable tourism. The book recognizes the importance of coherence between local practices and global strategies. In particular, the importance of creating a sustainable tourism model through environmental monitoring, resource conservation and territorial planning is emphasized.

R. Buckley[2] analyzes the gap between theoretical concepts and real practices. The author shows that sustainability policies often remain in political statements, but there are shortcomings in their practical implementation. According to the analysis, the involvement of local communities, environmental certification and monitoring of tourist facilities are effective tools for achieving environmental sustainability.

Authors B. Bramwell and B. Lane[3] reveal the importance of effective public policies, coordination between stakeholders and institutional approaches in managing sustainable tourism. They justify the need to develop multi-level governance mechanisms between governments, the private sector and civil society to improve environmental governance. The studies cite the experience of Norway and Canada as important examples.

The article analyzes the role of environmental governance in ensuring the competitiveness of tourist areas. T. Mihalic[4] lists environmental infrastructure, waste recycling systems and environmental education as important factors. The author also proves with theoretical and practical evidence that it is possible to ensure environmental sustainability by adapting sustainable tourism policies to local conditions.

J. Saarinen[5] in his study analyzes the historical evolution of the concept of tourism and sustainability. He shows that it is difficult to solve environmental sustainability with a single approach in the tourism sector, as each region has its own unique ecological, cultural and economic characteristics. According to the author, the development of environmental policies based on regional approaches is more effective in achieving sustainability.

S. Becken and D. Simmons[6] study the types of energy consumption in tourism activities and their impact on the environment. The authors believe that energy conservation, the use of renewable sources and the introduction of "green technologies" in tourism infrastructure can reduce the ecological footprint. The study was conducted on the example of New Zealand tourist areas, and the results can be applied to other regions.

The UN[7] manual has developed policy strategies to ensure environmental sustainability in the global tourism sector. The document proposes 12 priority areas for governments: resource management, environmental tax policy, community involvement and promoting sustainable tourism through the education system. This resource serves as a global guide for policymakers and researchers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research work, methods widely used in scientific research methodology were used. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods were widely used, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, and in analysis, synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Sustainable Tourism Development in Uzbekistan: Institutional and Regional Cases. Uzbekistan, situated at the crossroads of ancient trade routes, is rapidly emerging as a tourism destination, drawing attention not only for its cultural heritage but also for its growing commitment to sustainability. In recent years, national and regional authorities have begun to integrate environmental priorities into tourism policy, supported by a broader agenda of sustainable development. This section explores the institutional landscape, strategic efforts, and on-the-ground practices that illustrate Uzbekistan's progress in embedding ecological sustainability into tourism development.

One of the most significant steps was the inclusion of sustainable tourism in the country's 2022–2026 Strategy for Green Growth and Environmental Protection, which outlines specific goals for biodiversity conservation, climate adaptation, and sustainable resource use in tourism zones. This strategic shift has led to the designation of new protected areas and the strengthening of ecotourism as a state priority. Among these, the Priaralye National Nature Park in Karakalpakstan stands out as a flagship initiative. Located in the ecologically fragile post-Aral Sea zone, the park spans 3,165.95 hectares and is divided into three functional zones: a reserve core (2,317.86 ha), a recreational area (488.72 ha), and a business-use area (399.37 ha). The park exemplifies an integrated approach where environmental conservation, scientific research, and tourism coexist.

Another notable example is the development of community-based tourism (CBT) in mountain regions like the Nuratau-Kyzylkum biosphere reserve and the villages around the Chimgan-Charvak zone. These initiatives empower local residents to host tourists, engage in nature interpretation, and promote traditional lifestyles while minimizing environmental impact. CBT practices are supported by NGOs and international donors, offering training in waste management, renewable energy use, and biodiversity protection.

At the urban level, cities like Tashkent and Samarkand are making strides in “green city” branding. Hotels and guesthouses are increasingly participating in national certification programs that promote energy efficiency, water-saving technologies, and the use of local organic produce. Educational institutions, such as the Tashkent State University of Economics, have incorporated sustainability modules into tourism curricula, preparing future professionals to address environmental issues from both operational and strategic perspectives.

S. Safaeva emphasizes in her analysis of Karakalpakstan, infrastructure development is not just a prerequisite for tourism accessibility, but a strategic lever for long-term sustainability. Without roads, utilities, and basic logistics, ecotourism initiatives struggle to reach their full potential, particularly in environmentally vulnerable zones.

Despite these promising developments, several challenges persist. Environmental education among tourists remains limited, and enforcement of ecological standards is uneven, especially in remote areas. Additionally, infrastructure investments often prioritize short-term growth over long-term sustainability, posing risks to natural assets. Addressing these gaps requires a coordinated multi-stakeholder approach, combining state policy, academic leadership, and grassroots participation.

Uzbekistan's evolving model of sustainable tourism illustrates how post-Soviet countries can reshape their tourism sectors in harmony with environmental imperatives. These efforts, while still nascent, offer a foundation for more advanced collaboration with international experts and institutions, including comparative policy learning from Mediterranean contexts such as Catalonia, where climate resilience and sustainable coastal tourism are already institutionalized.

Comparative approaches: Mediterranean and Central Asian models. Comparing approaches to ecological sustainability in tourism between Mediterranean and Central Asian regions reveals valuable lessons in both policy design and implementation. While the geographical and socio-economic contexts differ considerably, both regions face the common challenge of aligning tourism growth with environmental protection in the context of climate change and resource constraints.

In the Mediterranean, particularly in Catalonia, Spain, tourism has long been a major economic sector. However, the intensive development of coastal and urban areas in the 1990s and early 2000s led to severe environmental degradation, prompting a shift toward sustainability. Professor Oscar Saladié, a leading expert in tourism and climate risk analysis at Rovira i Virgili University (URV), has highlighted the importance of adaptive management in coastal destinations, the role of universities in sustainab...Catalonia's success in transitioning to more sustainable tourism is supported by strong institutional mechanisms:

Municipal governments enforce zoning regulations that limit overdevelopment;

Protected natural parks (e.g., Delta de l'Ebre) are co-managed with environmental scientists and tourism experts;

Certification systems such as the Biosphere Responsible Tourism label are used to incentivize sustainable business practices.

In contrast, Central Asia — and Uzbekistan in particular — is still in the earlier stages of developing such integrated systems. Nevertheless, Uzbekistan benefits from a relatively low baseline of environmental impact in many rural areas, and from recent government support for green transformation. Unlike Catalonia, where the emphasis is now on retro-fitting and mitigation, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to embed sustainability from the outset in its developing tourism sector.

One notable difference lies in the governance model. While Spain applies decentralized, locally driven frameworks for sustainability, Uzbekistan's approach remains more centralized, with state programs guiding regional efforts. Both models have advantages: the Catalan model fosters grassroots innovation and local accountability, while Uzbekistan's system allows for rapid policy coordination across wide territories.

Educational institutions in both countries are playing a growing role. URV's Faculty of Tourism is a hub for research and training on climate risk, while universities in Uzbekistan — such as Tashkent State University of Economics — are beginning to institutionalize sustainable tourism education, often in collaboration with international experts like Professor Saladié.

By bridging experiences between Mediterranean Europe and Central Asia, this article aims to highlight replicable strategies and inspire regional innovation. Uzbekistan can benefit from Catalonia's regulatory tools, community engagement methods, and academic frameworks. At the same time, Spain may draw insight from the more centralized mobilization of national initiatives in Central Asia and the potential for scalable green tourism models in emerging destinations.

Barriers, Opportunities, and Policy Recommendations. Despite growing recognition of the need for sustainability in tourism, the practical implementation of ecological principles remains uneven across regions. Both Uzbekistan and Mediterranean destinations such as Catalonia face structural and operational barriers, though the nature and severity of these constraints differ.

In Uzbekistan, the main barriers include:

Limited technical expertise in sustainable planning and environmental monitoring at the regional level;

Insufficient coordination between tourism development agencies and environmental regulators;

Low awareness among domestic tourists about sustainability practices;

Fragmented funding mechanisms, especially for remote or ecologically sensitive destinations such as the Priaralye zone.

In Mediterranean Europe, particularly Spain, the challenges are more related to managing the legacy of over-tourism, such as:

Urban saturation and housing conflicts in popular destinations like Barcelona;

Degradation of coastal ecosystems due to historical under-regulation;

Balancing economic dependency on tourism with long-term environmental restoration goals.

However, both regions now find themselves at a turning point — with opportunities for policy innovation and cross-regional learning. Uzbekistan can capitalize on:

- Its greenfield advantage in many tourism areas, allowing sustainability to be designed from the beginning;

- Growing international collaboration, including academic partnerships and development aid for ecotourism;

- A younger generation of tourism professionals who are being trained with sustainability principles in mind.

For Mediterranean regions, opportunities lie in:

- Advancing climate-adaptive tourism models, including early-warning systems and seasonal redistribution of tourist flows;

- Deepening university–community partnerships to support local innovation;

- Leveraging digital platforms for eco-labeling, tourist education, and feedback systems.

Policy Recommendations:

1. Integrate sustainability into national and regional tourism strategies through enforceable planning standards and periodic environmental audits.

2. Enhance academic and institutional collaboration between countries with differing levels of tourism maturity to support two-way knowledge exchange.

3. Develop community-based models that place local residents at the center of tourism governance, supported by clear ecological performance indicators.

4. Invest in green infrastructure, especially in protected and remote areas, ensuring basic services meet ecological standards.

5. Foster climate resilience planning by including vulnerability assessments in tourism development projects, as practiced in Catalonia.

By combining the strategic foresight of Mediterranean models with the emerging energy and adaptability of Central Asian destinations, a more balanced, inclusive, and ecologically responsible tourism future can be realized.

CONCLUSION AND RECCOMENDATIONS

Ecological sustainability in tourism is no longer a conceptual ideal but a strategic necessity. As global tourism rebounds from pandemic-era disruptions and faces increasing climate volatility, destinations must embed environmental considerations into every facet of planning, development, and operations. This article has explored the evolving efforts of Uzbekistan to align its tourism growth with ecological principles — from state-led initiatives in protected areas to grassroots ecotourism and academic.

In parallel, Mediterranean regions such as Catalonia offer a mature model of sustainability, born from the lessons of over-tourism and environmental strain. Professor Oscar Saladié's contributions, particularly on climate risk and the educational role of universities, reinforce the importance of evidence-based policymaking and transdisciplinary approaches. The Catalan model emphasizes decentralized governance, regulatory innovation, and climate adaptation — areas from which emerging destinations can draw.

By synthesizing insights from both contexts, the article advocates for mutual learning and co-creation of tourism strategies that are both economically viable and ecologically sound. Cross-regional collaboration between academic institutions, public agencies, and tourism practitioners can help build a more resilient and responsible global tourism system — one that honors the environment not as a backdrop to the travel experience, but as its foundation.

LIST OF USED REFERENCES:

1. Gössling, S., Hall, C. M., & Weaver, D. (2009). "Sustainable Tourism Futures: Perspectives on Systems, Restructuring and Innovations". Routledge.
2. Buckley, R. (2012). "Sustainable Tourism: Research and Reality". *Annals of Tourism Research*, 39(2), 528–546.
3. Bramwell, B. & Lane, B. (2011). "Critical Research on the Governance of Tourism and Sustainability". *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 19(4–5), 411–421.
4. Mihalic, T. (2000). "Environmental Management of a Tourist Destination: A Factor of Tourism Competitiveness". *Tourism Management*, 21(1), 65–78.
5. Saarinen, J. (2006). "Traditions of Sustainability in Tourism Studies". *Annals of Tourism Research*, 33(4), 1121–1140.
6. Becken, S. & Simmons, D. G. (2002). "Understanding Energy Consumption Patterns of Tourist Attractions and Activities". *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 10(4), 367–397.
7. UNEP & WTO (2005). "Making Tourism More Sustainable – A Guide for Policy Makers". United Nations.
8. Gössling, S., & Hall, C. M. (2021). *Tourism and sustainability: Development, globalisation and new tourism in the Third World*. Routledge.
9. Saladié, O., & Santos-Lacueva, R. (2016). The role of climate change in the future planning of coastal tourism: A Mediterranean perspective. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 77, 477–481.
10. United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). (2023). *Sustainable Tourism for Development Guidelines*.
11. Uzbekistan Committee for Tourism. (2023). *National Strategy for Ecotourism and Green Growth (2022–2026)*.
12. Zoltan, J., & McKercher, B. (2015). Analysing intra-destination movements and activity participation with GPS tracking technology. *Tourism Geographies*, 17(1), 19–35.
13. UNDP Uzbekistan. (2022). *Ecotourism development in Karakalpakstan: Challenges and solutions*.
14. Hall, C. M. (2019). Constructing sustainable tourism development: The 2030 Agenda and the limits of policy integration. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 27(7), 1044–1058.
15. Saladié, O., & Gutiérrez, A. (2022). Education for Sustainability in Tourism Studies. *Tourism Planning & Development*, 19(4), 375–392.
16. Ministry of Ecology, Uzbekistan. (2024). *Report on Protected Areas and Biodiversity under Tourism Use*.
17. World Bank. (2023). *Green Growth and Sustainable Tourism in Emerging Economies*.
18. Safaeva, S. R. (2024). Enhancing tourism through infrastructure development in Karakalpakstan: A path to sustainable growth. *Marketing jurnali*, 7(7), 16–19.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 6

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
